

reference strains. Production of H₂S from cysteine, reducing sugar, and production of acid from starch and rhamnose differentiated the 12 isolates from *Pantoea ananas* (*E. ananas*). Six isolates induced discoloration of palea when inoculated at flowering stage by spraying. The rate of discolored grains on a panicle was 2.1–12.6%, which varied based on isolate, age of the rice plant, and environmental conditions (mainly temperature and moisture) for inoculation (Azegami et al 1983). The six selected strains isolated from discolored grains were identified as *P. agglomerans* by Biolog, which confirmed the two reference strains as *P. agglomerans* with similarity indices of 0.611 and 0.930 (Table 2).

The causal organism of palea browning in Zhejiang Province has been phenotypically identified as *P.*

Table 2. Identity of causal bacterium of palea browning of rice by Biolog.

Code of isolate	Biolog identification	Similarity index
CB98301	<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	0.971
CB97311	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.930
CB98370	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.911
CB97303	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.894
CB97318	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.863
CB98369	<i>P. agglomerans</i>	0.827

agglomerans. It can be concluded that it is the same causal organism reported in Japan in 1983.

References

- Azegami K, Ozaki K, Matsuda A. 1983. Bacterial palea browning, a new disease of rice caused by *Erwinia herbicola*. Bull. Natl. Inst. Agric. Sci. Ser. C 39:1–12.
- Gavini F, Mergaert J, Beji A, Mielcarek C, Izard D, Kersters K, Ley J de. 1989. Transfer of *Enterobacter agglomerans* (Beijerinck 1888) Ewing and Fife 1972 to *Pantoea* gen. nov. as *Pantoea agglomerans* comb. nov. and description of *Pantoea dispersa* sp. nov. Int. J. Syst. Bacteriol. 39(3):337–345.
- Kim YC, Kim KC, Cho BH. 1989. Palea browning disease of rice caused by *Erwinia herbicola* and ice nucleation activity of the pathogenic bacteria. Korean J. Plant Pathol. 5(1):72–79.
- Mew TW, Misra JK. 1994. A manual of rice seed health testing. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. 220 p.
- Xie GL. 1996. Characterization of *Pseudomonas* spp. and other bacterial species associated with rice seeds. PhD thesis, University of the Philippines Los Banos, Philippines. 170 p.

Expression of *Bt* genes under control of different promoters in rice at vegetative and flowering stages

R.M. Aguda, K. Datta, J. Tu, S.K. Datta, and M.B. Cohen, IRRI E-mail: m.cohen@cgiar.org

Toxin-encoding genes from the bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) have been widely used in plant transformation to confer resistance to insect pests. These genes have been placed under the control of various promoters. Some, such as the cauliflower mosaic virus (CaMV) 35S and rice actin promoters, are constitutive promoters, that is, they drive gene expression in most tissues at most stages of plant development. Other promoters are tissue-specific, such as the maize phosphoenolpyruvate carboxylase (PEPC) promoter, which is active only in tissues that are photosynthetically active, and the maize tryptophan synthase alpha subunit promoter, which is active in pith. To achieve adequate and sustainable insect control with *Bt* genes, the associated promoter should provide strong gene expression in tissues attacked by target pests during all stages of plant development that are attacked by the pests (Cohen et al 2000). In some cases, it may

also be useful to avoid toxin gene expression in tissues not attacked by target pests, such as roots or grain.

In rice, the principal target pests for control by *Bt* genes are the yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), striped stem borer (SSB) *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker), and leafhoppers such as *Marasmia patnalis* Guenée. Alinia et al (2000) found that a rice line transformed with *Bt cry1Ab* toxin gene under control of the PEPC promoter was highly resistant to stem borers and leaf-feeding pests at the vegetative stage, but that toxin titer and insect resistance dropped substantially at the flowering stage. In this study, we examined the resistance at the vegetative and flowering stages of *cry1Ab*-transformed rice lines with the CaMV, actin, and pith-specific promoters. These lines were previously found to be resistant to YSB at the vegetative stage (Datta et al 1998, Tu et al 1998).

Lines with the pith-specific and CaMV 35S promoter were in the background of variety CBII, and the line with the actin promoter was variety IR72. All lines were homozygous-positive for the *cry1Ab* gene. Nontransgenic plants of CBII and IR72 were used as controls. Bioassays were conducted in petri dishes using cut stems for YSB and SSB and cut leaves for *M. patnalis*, with one stem or leaf per petri dish. Six first-instar stem borer larvae or second-instar *M. patnalis* larvae were placed in each petri dish, and the number of dead, live, and unrecovered larvae was recorded after 4 d. One stem and one leaf were tested from each of 75 plants of each *cry1Ab* line at the vegetative stage. Another stem and leaf from 50 of these plants were tested at the booting stage, and another stem and leaf from 25 plants at the flowering stage. Three stems or leaves were tested from one CBII and IR72 control plant at each growth stage. Each petri dish

was considered a replicate. Petri dishes were arranged in a completely randomized design. Whole-plant bioassays of plants at the vegetative, booting, and flowering stages were conducted with YSB. At each growth stage, eight plants of each *cryIAb* line and eight control plants of CBII and IR72 were infested with 25 first-instar YSB larvae. Four plants were dissected after 4 d and four plants after 25 d. All data were analyzed by analysis of variance, and arc-sine-square root-transformed means were compared by the LSD test.

In the petri dish assays, larval survival on all three *cryIAb* lines was significantly lower than on control lines at the vegetative and flowering stages (Fig. 1). For both SSB and *M. patnalis*, survival was significantly lower on the line with the CaMV 35S promoter than on that with the pith-specific promoter. In the whole-plant assays, YSB larval survival was significantly lower on all three *cryIAb* lines than on control plants at both growth stages (Fig. 2). Similar results were also obtained at the booting stage in both the petri dish and whole-plant assays (data not shown).

Our results demonstrate that *cryIAb* lines with the actin, CaMV 35S, and pith-specific promoters retain resistance to stem borers and leaffolders at the flowering stage. Quantification of toxin titer by immunological methods would provide a more sensitive test of whether there is a decline in toxin titer at the flowering stage. However, it is apparent that any toxin decline in these lines is much less substantial than that observed by Alinia et al (2000) in a *cryIAb* rice line with the PEPC promoter. Because toxin expression can vary greatly among transgenic lines containing the same construct, additional lines must be tested before general conclusions can be drawn.

References

- Alinia F, Ghareyazie B, Rubia LG, Bennett J, Cohen MB. 2000. Effect of plant age, larval age, and fertilizer treatment on resistance of a *cryIAb*-transformed aromatic rice to lepidopterous stem borers and foliage feeders. *J. Econ. Entomol.* 93:484–493.
- Cohen MB, Gould F, Bentur JS. 2000. *Bt* rice: practical steps to sustainable use. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 25(2):4–10.
- Datta K, Vasquez A, Tu J, Torrizo L, Alam MF, Oliva N, Abrigo E, Khush GS, Datta SK. 1998. Constitutive and tissue-specific differential expression of the *cryIAb* gene in transgenic

Fig. 1. Survival (mean $\pm$ SE) of stem borer and leaffolder larvae after 4 d on cut stems and leaves of *cryIAb* and control lines. Means within a growth stage, species, and variety (CBII or IR72) sharing the same letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$, LSD test).

Fig. 2. Survival (mean $\pm$ SE) of YSB larvae in *cryIAb* and control lines in whole-plant bioassays. Means within a growth stage and variety (CBII or IR72) sharing the same letters are not significantly different ($P > 0.05$, LSD test).

rice plants conferring resistance to rice insect pest. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 97:20–30.

Tu J, Datta K, Alam MF, Fan Y, Khush GS, Datta SK. 1998. Expression and function of hybrid

Bt toxin gene in transgenic rice conferring resistance to insect pest. *Plant Biotechnol.* 15:195–203.